

Authors: Dr Miranda Geelhoed, Professor Jill Robbie

Dear Mr Dunne and Mr Hutchinson,

On the 25th of February, Dr Miranda Geelhoed, research associate on the RESPECT Project (Rapid Engagement with Stressed Peatland Environments and Communities in Transformation) attended a workshop organised by NatureScot on the future of Peatland ACTION. At the end of the workshop, participants were asked to share any further views via email. We would like to take this opportunity to share some initial views on the proposed changes to Peatland ACTION funding and make key connections with research under the RESPECT project.

The LUNZ Hub's RESPECT project

The interdisciplinary Rapid Engagement with Stressed Peatland Environments and Communities in Transformation (RESPECT) project is affiliated with the Land Use for Net Zero, Nature and People (LUNZ) Hub and is funded by the UKRI Land Use for Net Zero programme. RESPECT aims to produce data, methods, landholder tools and proposals for governance reforms to change agricultural practices on peatland. RESPECT brings together researchers across Scotland and England with expertise in the natural and social sciences, humanities and law. RESPECT will also produce the Peatland Triage Tool (PTT), providing decision-support for landowners, land managers, farmers and crofters (collectively 'landholders') seeking to undertake peatland restoration. Upon completion, RESPECT will be able to provide a solid evidence base, and tools to inform land use decisions in relation to the restoration and sustainable management of agricultural peatlands.

In the summary report of key feedback received from stakeholders it is noted that there is a "need to be clearer on the science and rationale for protection, restoration and management of our peatland". RESPECT will provide evidence in this area as well as support wider thinking around Scotland's approach to peatland restoration including policy and financial levers.

Note that NatureScot is a formal project partner of RESPECT (lead contact: Ross Lilley, Head of Natural Resource Management).

Expand the pipeline of designed/investable projects

Expansion of the pipeline and increase of staffing capacity for Peatland ACTION and partners will be useful for increasing the net delivery rate of peatland restoration. However, without consideration of issues that inhibit access to funding, an increase in capacity will most likely be felt in areas and holdings that already are most likely to undertake restoration, e.g., large privately owned estates. Key barriers to integrating peatland restoration into small to medium-sized agricultural holdings will not be addressed by proposed changes, for example, impacts of restoration on eligibility of producers to receive agricultural payments, landowner consent in the case of crofting and tenant farmers and low capacity to make informed decisions about undertaking peatland restoration via Peatland ACTION or Peatland Code. RESPECT will work with landholders to better understand potential synergies and trade-offs of peatland restoration and develop governance reforms in support of peatland restoration on agricultural land.

A shift in focus: benefits and outcomes

As discussed during the workshop, Peatland ACTION proposes to review the assessment criteria for projects from 2026/2027, in particular, to shift the focus from hectare outputs to benefits and outcomes. We are, in principle, supportive of such an approach that addresses environmental and social aspects of peatland management and restoration in a more holistic way. This will also contribute to a more effective targeting of public funds to deliver on multiple policy objectives. RESPECT is currently working on the mapping of laws and policies in relation to peatland restoration in Scotland which may inform such an integrated approach.

We make several initial observations in relation to the scope of criteria to assess benefits:

- The feedback report mentions a potential ‘themed approach’ to funding allocation depending on the types of benefits generated. A focus on carbon would prioritise large scale, landscape projects with

high hectareage. In this regard, it is, however, noted that carbon sequestration potential may vary across hectares and at different points in time. A clear understanding of the temporal and spatial development and resilience of these landscapes is vital for intervention design. For example, this could allow for targeting of restoration areas where local heating will not overcome benefits of restoration in the short to medium term, thereby increasing the net benefits of peatland restoration. RESPECT will establish the current and future physical capacity of land in the Forth catchment to contribute to net zero and prioritise areas for peatland restoration.

- There is a need for explicit inclusion of potential benefits from and for the historic environment, designated or not, in the assessment of funding applications. The feedback report only references heritage in a comment on archaeological constraints by local government. This represents a narrow understanding of the historic environment. Long-term information (100s to 1000s years) on peatland development is available from the historic environment through palaeoenvironmental records; a heritage asset providing an opportunity to inform and contextualise long-term restoration planning and development of realistic objectives. Note the Peatland Code’s inclusion of historic environment features (sec. 1.4). RESPECT is currently collating historic and new data to elucidate patterns of peatland through space and time, thus being able to contribute to evidencing of benefits.
- The feedback report (briefly) mentions community benefits as considerations when assessing funding applications. This point did, however, not come through strongly in the workshop. It is noted that there is an increasing expectation in Scotland that natural capital projects deliver wide community benefits. We reference the Scottish Government’s [Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement](#), the Scottish Land Commission’s work and [guidance on community benefits](#) and inclusive [governance models](#), and the Scottish Government’s [Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital](#). RESPECT will undertake qualitative research with communities and work with Community Land Scotland on what community benefits are expected or desired from peatland restoration, and how monetary and nonmonetary benefits are valued.

We do note that there may be tensions between the proposed shift to a focus on benefits, the Scottish Government’s area-based targets for peatland restoration and the proposals to simplify the process and reduce bureaucracy. We echo calls in the feedback report on the need for transparent decision-making on the allocation of peatland ACTION funds to demonstrate how public money is used and how projects deliver on diverse policy objectives and targets. Whilst it may be useful in some instances to use designations, including historic and environmental designations, to evidence how projects would be able to generate multiple benefits, it is important that applicants have flexibility to provide evidence of economic, environmental, historic, cultural and community benefits in other ways, including in relation to local priorities. RESPECT will gather data on expected/desired monetary and non-monetary benefits from peatland restoration for broader land interest groups in the Forth catchment.

As noted by some participants during the workshop, there is a risk that the shift in approach will lead to increased administrative burdens on applicants. Potential issues of capacity may disproportionately affect more complex and riskier projects, for example, projects on agricultural land that are smaller in scale or projects that involve multiple parties. Those projects may be less likely to attract private finance and would, therefore, greatly benefit from public support. This is not a reason against the change of focus towards benefits/outcomes, but there is a need to adequately support projects in the developmental stages including application preparation. In this regard, reform of the Project Development Support Scheme (PDSS) should be considered. We understand that, so far, PDSS eligibility and funding criteria may have favoured large-scale projects. Reform could allow for the scheme to be awarded more widely, supporting capacity building and the creation of lasting partnerships. In addition, steps should be taken towards simplification of application processes, e.g., aligning timetables with other deadlines such as AECS or financial year starts.

Other reflections: just transition issues and the role of private finance

Proposed changes to support expansion of peatland restoration in Scotland include an increased focus on private finance to complement public funds. We understand that this will involve a review to reduce the

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maximum intervention rate for capital costs to 50% by 2030. In this regard, it is noted that data on the longterm viability and resilience of carbon-credit funded peatland restoration projects is still lacking.

We also emphasise that RESPECT will be working with landholders to assess the potential and challenges of peatland restoration pathways which will include different financing options. An increased focus on private finance without an in-depth understanding of barriers for landholders and consequences for other communities and environmental factors is not without risk. This is particularly relevant when considered from a just transition perspective as, so far, groups like small-scale and tenanted landholders, crofters and communities, have experienced obstacles in accessing finance. A benefit from merging public and private funding could be that Peatland Code funding is more likely to reach areas that currently see little private investment. However, in relation to blended finance models we do raise significant concerns about government underwriting the carbon market, particularly where this means financial risks solely lie with the public purse instead of investors.

Lastly, we note that an increase in focus on private finance puts emphasis on the need for a regulatory framework to direct investment, monitor potential negative social and environmental impacts and ensure that investment delivers public, private and community benefits.

We would welcome an opportunity to discuss this further and explore opportunities for us to learn from Peatland ACTION's work and for Peatland ACTION to integrate learning from RESPECT's interdisciplinary research as it is being developed.

Yours sincerely,

Jill Robbie

Jill Robbie, on behalf of the RESPECT research team

RESPECT Project Lead

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